

TECHNIQUES AND METHODS FOR IMPLEMENTING THE TASKS OF CULTURAL EDUCATION IN THE RUSSIAN LANGUAGE LESSONS

Umarova Dilfuza Mamatkulovna

Researcher of Samarkand State University veterinary medicine of
livestock and biotechnologies, Samarkand
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ABSTRACT

An analysis of current trends and problems in the development of higher education has shown that both domestic and foreign schools pay special attention to the educational side of the content of education. High demands are placed not only on the student, but also on his spiritual and moral character, attitude towards colleagues, society and the environment. Currently, higher education does not see an alternative to the process of humanization of student training. From the standpoint of the culturological approach, today a special role belongs to the philosophical and methodological understanding of pedagogical science and practice, a holistic, integrative, integrated method of research and design of educational systems becomes a priority.

The methodology of the lessons, the first and main goal of which is the formation of cultural competence, is only taking shape, therefore, it is more often presented in the form of separate lessons or their fragments. One of the methods of work that allows to realize the goals of the formation of cultural competence is "etymological studies" at the beginning of each lesson. Students prepare "etymological sketches" about the words Russian, Russia, city, village, street, doctor and doctor, architect and architect, school, gymnasium and college, etc., about local toponyms Oskol, Vorskla, Nezhegol, Maslova Pier, Grayvoron, etc. The effectiveness of similar, at first glance, quite traditional exercises is not appreciated by all philologists, and meanwhile, turning to etymological analysis in the lesson invariably arouses the interest of adolescents, since it allows you to look at familiar words from an unusual side, "warms up" interest by the way, to the study of the language, expands the linguistic horizons and contributes to the formation of cultural competence. Another "effective" technique is cross-language comparisons.

Thus, the border position of the Belgorod region determines the significance and relevance in the language lessons of Russian-Ukrainian comparisons: phonetic, lexical, grammatical, in particular, the presence or absence of the vocative case, Ukrainisms in the speech of fellow countrymen, in fiction, "Belgorod-Ukrainian" toponyms: Belaya Krinita,

Chervonodibrovka, the same Grayvoron, etc. Another way that does not require the use of any additional means is also effective - passing socio- and linguo-cultural comments on the texts used in the lessons (and objects for explanation and commenting in any text will be found, if you look at it with a "philologically armed eye"; it is important for the commentator himself to be in "philological full armor"): for example, even the textbook stanza from "Eugene Onegin", which begins with the words Winter! The peasant, triumphant ..., will set before the students (but first before the teacher) the task of clarifying the lexical meanings of the words kibitka, irradiation, sash, sled, comment on the words yard boy, bug (why with a lowercase letter, and not with a capital letter, how, it would seem necessary), and option [1].

The upbringing of the student is carried out during the entire educational process, but the mother tongue is the basis of the upbringing system. The lesson of the native language conceals in unlimited opportunities for raising a student as a citizen of his fatherland.

The main thing is to instill in the student a sense of unity with his native land, nature, to arouse interest in the history of the region, to instill a responsible attitude to deeds and actions.

"What goes around comes around!" says folk wisdom. How important it is to sow the field with good seeds on time, and for teachers to sow the good seeds of aesthetic consciousness in the souls of students.

Teachers select highly artistic texts of Russian writers and poets, accompanying the richest language material with interesting tasks aimed at the formation of aesthetic ideas, the development of creative thinking.

Let's give an example: students are invited to read the words from E. Trutneva's poem "Goodbye, summer":

Played out, in the clearing, the wind, in, whirled, forest) sundress, red, aspen; and, leaf, with, winds, birches, and, golden, bee, Christmas tree, flies, prickly, over.

Next, the teacher suggests compiling two sentences with homogeneous members, putting the highlighted words first in the sentence. The guys do not immediately get poetic lines, and the teacher comes to the rescue. We offer possible types of tasks:

Find the rhyming words in the first sentence.

- Swap the words in the first sentence so that you get two poetic lines.

Similar work is carried out with the second proposal. It is very important that the students experience pleasure from the result. After all, only success and positive emotions move them up the educational ladder.

In addition to rich language material, teachers offer reproductions of paintings by great Russian artists, masters of landscape and portrait (I.I. Levitan, I.I. Shishkin, I.E. Grabar, V.M. Vasnetsov, I.E. Repin, V.A. Serov, A.A. Plastova), accompanying each with a text by art historians. It is difficult for students to write an essay based on a picture, but there is a wonderful example in the textbook - the text of an art critic. In addition to it, a conversation is conducted on the content of the picture. All this together tunes in to creativity, the student is imbued with the content of the picture, feels gratitude for the artist's work.

Working with poems by great Russian poets, with paintings by great artists, instills in students an artistic flair, a sense of rhyme and a desire to create. Lebedev V. A. Russian language as a cultural and historical environment.

The tasks of socio- and ethno-cultural education and upbringing can be solved through a wide and multifaceted use at different stages of education in all lessons - and in the lessons of the native language, of course, in the first place - lexical, lexicographic, etymological data, including local history, analysis of texts reflecting the peculiarities of national thinking, social and speech behavior and the Russian mentality as a whole. This aspect of the study of the Russian language is being actively developed at the present time by ethnophilology and ethnoculturology.

Formation of a sense of belonging to the historical past of the region, Motherland, nature.

The content of many texts of the textbook of the Russian language allows the formation of such moral qualities of the student as a feeling of love for nature, a sense of responsibility for what surrounds you, a sense of belonging to the historical past of the region. Consider some exercises that contribute to the formation of a sense of belonging to the historical past of the region, Motherland, nature. Students are asked to read the text and reflect on its content.

No other country in the world has as many birches as ours. She is dear to the Russian people. Birch in songs, and in riddles, and in fairy tales. And how many rivers, villages are named after our green beauty! Our people love the birch both for its beauty and for the benefits it brings [3].

Together with the teacher, students try to answer questions and determine the topic and main idea of the text. Question of the teacher: "What is the most important thing the author wanted to say in these lines!" makes students think about the image of a birch and its significance in the life of a Russian person.

Under the guidance of a teacher, students try to find answers to questions about the theme and main idea of this poem; they argue whether we have the right to fully use nature, how a person should behave in nature.

There is another tool in the work of a language teacher that allows you to enter information of a cultural nature - an appeal to the problems of Russian speech etiquette. Increasingly, we meet (both in real life and in the methodological literature describing this practice) successful experiences of including information on the history and practice of speech etiquette, presentation and linguistic justification of stereotypes of Russian speech behavior in the Russian language lesson, in particular with the help of proverbs, sayings, stable expressions, phraseological units. An ethnocultural orientation to the lesson of the Russian language is also given by exercises based on the interpretation of Russian words - realities, naming the characteristic details of national life, folklore, history, introducing at least a minimum amount of information on toponymy and onomastics - by the way, this material is in textbooks and teaching aids - even the new generation - is practically not represented, despite the generally recognized fact of the special interest of students of any age in onomastic material, especially in regions, - and its indisputable educational value.

Lessons in the formation of cultural competence also require a revision of the existing methodology for organizing Russian language lessons, testing and including in the structure of the lesson new methods and forms of working with the word that are more in line with the new direction [5].

Thus, the following is essential:

- a) to form the cultural competence of students declared by modern educational standards;
- b) develop the language personality of the student;
- c) to carry out integration in the teaching of institution disciplines and, which is especially important from the point of view of the problem under consideration,
- d) put into practice a cultural approach to teaching the native (Russian) language.

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